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The Development of Students' Psycho-Emotional Intelligence in the Context of the Transformation of the Modern Educational Environment

Svitlana Tolochko

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, chief researcher of the laboratory of extracurricular education Institute of Problems on Education of the NAES of Ukraine,

9 M. Berlinsky St., Kyiv, 04060, e-mail: svitlana-tsv@ukr.net;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9262-2311>

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***Abstract.** The article reveals the theoretical foundations, empirical approaches, and pedagogical conditions for the development of students' psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) in the context of dynamic modern educational environment transformations. In view of the challenges posed by digitalization, emotional exhaustion, youth disorientation, and the growing need for soft skills, PEI emerges as a key personal competence of the 21st century. The essence and structure of PEI are defined, encompassing emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivational attitudes, and emotional expression. Contemporary academic sources are analyzed, confirming the importance of PEI in enhancing students' academic performance, psychological well-being, and professional readiness. The study identifies the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the effective development of PEI, such as an emotionally safe learning environment, reflective practices, situational learning, interpersonal interaction, and cross-cultural exchange. The authors present a vision of positive psycho-emotional intelligence as a factor in the value-based development of an individual. The article substantiates the prospects for integrating PEI into higher*

education curricula through the creation of interdisciplinary courses, digital tools, training programs, and pedagogical support. Particular attention is given to analyzing effective practices for developing PEI in Ukrainian institutions of higher education, including the use of reflective journals, role-playing, educational coaching, and emotionally oriented teaching methods. The study confirms that the development of students' psycho-emotional intelligence is not only an individual-psychological process but also a systemic pedagogical task requiring integration into higher education strategies. Conceptual guidelines are proposed for the incorporation of PEI into university educational policy, including institutional support for mental health, establishment of emotional competence centers, and inclusion of related competencies in higher education standards. Emphasis is placed on the need to integrate PEI into the training systems for future educators, managers, and professionals in the social and human sciences as a component of a new quality of education.

Keywords: *psycho-emotional intelligence, students, emotional competence, educational environment, self-regulation, pedagogical conditions, reflection.*

Формування психоемоційного інтелекту здобувачів освіти в умовах трансформації сучасного освітнього середовища

Толочко Світлана Вікторівна

доктор педагогічних наук, професор, головний науковий співробітник лабораторії позашкільної освіти Інституту проблем виховання, Національна академія педагогічних наук України, вул. М. Берлінського, 9, м. Київ, 04060,

e-mail: svitlana-tsv@ukr.net;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9262-2311>

Анотація. *У статті розкрито теоретичні засади, емпіричні підходи та педагогічні умови формування психоемоційного інтелекту (ПЕІ) здобувачів освіти в*

контексті динамічних трансформацій сучасного освітнього середовища. З огляду на виклики цифровізації, емоційного виснаження, дезорієнтації молоді та потреби в розвитку *soft skills*, ПЕІ постає як ключова особистісна компетентність XXI століття. Визначено сутність і структуру ПЕІ, яка охоплює емоційну усвідомленість, саморегуляцію, емпатію, мотиваційні установки та емоційну експресію. Проаналізовано сучасні наукові джерела, що підтверджують значення ПЕІ у підвищенні академічної успішності, психологічного благополуччя та професійної готовності здобувачів освіти. Виокремлено психолого-педагогічні умови ефективного формування ПЕІ: безпечне емоційне середовище, рефлексивні практики, ситуаційне навчання, міжособистісна взаємодія та кроскультурний обмін. Представлено авторське бачення позитивного психоемоційного інтелекту як чинника ціннісного розвитку особистості. Обґрунтовано перспективи впровадження ПЕІ у зміст вищої освіти через створення міждисциплінарних курсів, цифрових інструментів, тренінгових програм та педагогічної підтримки.

Особливу увагу приділено аналізу ефективних практик формування ПЕІ в українських закладах вищої освіти, зокрема використанню рефлексивних щоденників, рольових ігор, освітнього коучингу та емоційно орієнтованих методів викладання. Дослідження підтверджує, що формування психоемоційного інтелекту здобувачів освіти є не лише індивідуально-психологічним, а й системним педагогічним завданням, що потребує інтеграції в стратегії закладів вищої освіти. Запропоновано концептуальні орієнтири для впровадження ПЕІ в освітню політику ЗВО, зокрема через інституційну підтримку ментального здоров'я, створення центрів емоційної компетентності та включення відповідних компетентностей до стандартів вищої освіти. Акцент зроблено на необхідності інтеграції ПЕІ до системи підготовки майбутніх педагогів, управлінців і фахівців соціогуманітарної сфери як складника нової якості освіти.

Ключові слова: психоемоційний інтелект, здобувачі освіти, емоційна компетентність, освітнє середовище, саморегуляція, педагогічні умови, рефлексія.

General Problem Statement and Its Connection to Key Scientific or Practical Objectives. The rapid transformation of the modern educational environment—driven by digitalization, globalization, and the growing complexity of social interactions—necessitates a reevaluation of the foundational competencies required for successful student learning and professional integration. In this context, psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) is increasingly recognized as a critical determinant of students' academic success, emotional well-being, interpersonal communication, and overall personal development. Despite the evident importance of PEI, there remains a notable lack of systemic pedagogical frameworks aimed at its purposeful development within formal education. Contemporary curricula often emphasize cognitive and professional competencies, while emotional and psychological dimensions of learning are relegated to the periphery. This imbalance limits students' ability to manage stress, maintain motivation, build empathy, and form healthy social relationships—skills that are essential for functioning in dynamic and uncertain professional environments. Moreover, the challenges of the 21st century—such as information overload, virtual communication, emotional burnout, and socio-political instability—require individuals to possess not only intellectual capacity but also a well-developed ability to regulate emotions, recognize others' emotional states, and make emotionally intelligent decisions. These demands reinforce the urgency of integrating the development of psycho-emotional intelligence into the strategic priorities of higher education institutions.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. From a scientific standpoint, there is a growing body of international research confirming the impact of PEI on learning effectiveness, student engagement, and resilience. However, practical implementation remains fragmented, lacking unified methodological approaches, diagnostic tools, and pedagogical models tailored to specific educational contexts. Therefore, a key academic and practical objective is to investigate and define effective conditions, principles, and methods for fostering students' PEI within the realities of a transforming educational landscape. This problem is situated at the intersection of psychology, pedagogy, and educational innovation,

making it both theoretically significant and practically urgent. Addressing it can contribute to the design of holistic education models that support students not only as learners but as emotionally intelligent individuals prepared for life and work in a complex world.

In recent years, the issue of developing students' psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) has received significant attention in Ukrainian psychological and pedagogical scholarship. A comprehensive review of current literature reveals the growing scientific and practical interest in understanding the structure, development, and educational implications of PEI within the rapidly transforming educational landscape.

Several works focus on the methodological foundations and applied strategies for enhancing emotional intelligence in higher education. Notably, M. Avgustyuk (2022) presents detailed methodological recommendations aimed at increasing students' emotional competence, emphasizing reflective practices, self-regulation, and empathy-building exercises. Similarly, G. Murowska, G. Shevchenko, and Ya. Bezugla (2025) propose a holistic psycho-pedagogical framework for PEI development in higher education, grounded in integrative educational models and learner-centered approaches.

A number of studies examine the role of emotional intelligence in professional readiness. V. Zarytska (2014) underscores PEI as a key component of professional competence and psychological preparedness for the workforce. O. Romanovskyi, T. Hura, and O. Lapuzina (2024) explore how situational learning methods within university contexts can foster social and emotional competencies among future social workers.

The structural and psychological components of emotional intelligence have also been extensively investigated. N. Kalaytan, A. Makarenko and T. Starovoi (2020) compare the organization of students' PEI and creativity in humanities and technical specializations, revealing differences in emotional-cognitive processing. O. Liashch (2021) offers a developmental perspective, analyzing the genesis of emotional intelligence during adolescence based on empirical data. N. Tkachenko (2024), in turn, links emotional intelligence levels with coping strategies and social well-being, highlighting PEI's role in psychological resilience.

Several scholars have made significant contributions to the theoretical understanding of the concept. S. Marchuk (2021) and I. Mazokha (2020) provide conceptual analyses of emotional intelligence from psychological viewpoints, exploring its cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions. S. Tolochko (2024) positions psycho-emotional intelligence as a central construct in the educational process, connecting it to both academic achievement and personal development.

Particular attention has been paid to the early formation and diagnostics of emotional intelligence. S. Derevianko and S. Lavrenko (2020) develop methodological tools for assessing EI in children, offering insights relevant to early educational intervention. V. Kupchyshyna (2024) explores theoretical approaches to emotional intelligence in preschool children, emphasizing the need for developmental scaffolding and affective support.

From a pedagogical innovation standpoint, scholars such as S. Tolochko and O. Vasiuk (2024a, 2024b) stress the importance of cultivating positive psycho-emotional intelligence as a basis for multicultural education and personal growth. Their research proposes educational interventions aimed at fostering optimism, emotional literacy, and intercultural sensitivity. S. Berezka (2021) also contributes to this field by examining how the emotional intelligence of future special education professionals can be enhanced through tailored curricula and reflective practice.

Despite the growing number of empirical and theoretical studies, many authors (e.g., S. Tolochko, 2024; Tkachenko, 2024) agree that there is still a lack of systematic integration of PEI into mainstream educational standards. Moreover, diagnostic tools remain underdeveloped or inconsistently applied, and there is a pressing need for more evidence-based models and training programs that accommodate the emotional dimension of learning.

In conclusion, the reviewed body of literature substantiates the high relevance of psycho-emotional intelligence as a multidimensional phenomenon that significantly impacts students' academic performance, interpersonal communication, psychological

health, and professional orientation. However, the field still demands further interdisciplinary research, unified methodological frameworks, and scalable pedagogical solutions adapted to the contemporary educational context.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Despite the growing number of scientific studies on various aspects of the formation of students' psycho-emotional intelligence, there are still a number of unresolved issues in the modern scientific space that complicate the systematic implementation of this phenomenon in the educational process. In view of this, the paper will reveal the still insufficiently resolved problem of the peculiarities of the formation of psycho-emotional intelligence of students in the context of the transformation of the modern educational environment.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (task statement). The primary objective of this article is to explore the theoretical foundations and practical conditions for the development of students' psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) within the context of the evolving educational environment. The study seeks to identify the key factors influencing the formation of PEI, analyze existing pedagogical approaches and methodologies, and offer scientifically grounded recommendations for its purposeful integration into higher education.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the scientific results obtained.

The current research is dedicated to investigating the conceptual, theoretical, and methodological foundations of the development of psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) among students of higher education institutions in the context of systemic transformations in the educational environment. It draws upon recent scientific contributions by Ukrainian researchers as well as interdisciplinary studies that position PEI at the intersection of pedagogy, psychology, cognitive science, and educational innovation.

1. Theoretical Justification of the Role of Psycho-Emotional Intelligence in Education

The formation of PEI is increasingly viewed as a core dimension of holistic education, particularly relevant in the face of contemporary educational challenges, including emotional burnout, social instability, digital dependency, and the dehumanization of academic communication. As emphasized by S. Tolochko (2024), psycho-emotional intelligence encompasses a set of interconnected cognitive-affective abilities that enable an individual to recognize, understand, manage, and express emotions effectively in both interpersonal and intrapersonal contexts. These abilities include emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, emotional expression, and motivation.

The significance of PEI in education is not limited to emotional well-being. As S. Marchuk (2021) and I. Mazokha (2020) assert, it is also a fundamental personal resource that supports cognitive flexibility, critical thinking, and metacognition. PEI facilitates a student's ability to cope with stress, adapt to changing learning conditions, and navigate complex social relationships, which are especially pertinent during periods of rapid educational transformation.

V. Zarytska (2014) underscores the functional role of PEI as a core component of professional readiness. Her research highlights the influence of emotional intelligence on professional decision-making, teamwork, conflict resolution, and leadership – all of which are critical in emotionally intensive professions. These assertions provide a solid theoretical foundation for the development of PEI as a strategic objective of higher education.

2. Empirical Foundations and Diagnostics of Psycho-Emotional Intelligence

Recent empirical studies in Ukrainian psychological and pedagogical discourse provide a robust evidence base for examining the current state of PEI among students. M. Avgustyuk (2022) presents a structured methodological guide aimed at enhancing students' emotional intelligence, including exercises in self-observation, emotional regulation, and situational analysis. The guide incorporates elements of emotional coaching and reflexive dialogue, which proved effective in small-group instructional settings.

The diagnostics of PEI is an essential part of its development. S. Derevianko and S. Lavrenko (2020) propose several diagnostic tools, such as the “Emotional Recognition

Scale” and “Empathic Behavior Observation Cards,” which allow educators to assess key components of emotional intelligence in children and adolescents. O. Liashch’s (2021) dissertation represents one of the most comprehensive investigations into the genesis of emotional intelligence during adolescence, with an emphasis on the developmental peculiarities of emotional regulation, motivation, and empathy at various stages of youth maturation.

N. Tkachenko (2024) confirms the interdependence between PEI and students’ coping strategies. Her study revealed that students with high levels of PEI demonstrate increased social adaptability, lower levels of emotional exhaustion, and more constructive responses to academic challenges. These findings are empirically supported by statistical correlations between PEI subscales and self-reported well-being metrics.

3. Pedagogical Conditions and Models for PEI Formation

The synthesis of research from G. Murowska, G. Shevchenko and Ya. Bezugla (2025) demonstrates that the formation of PEI requires the establishment of a psychologically safe educational environment characterized by emotional acceptance, value-based interaction, and supportive communication. Their model integrates emotional-cognitive learning with metareflective practices and is built upon principles of humanistic pedagogy and neuropsychological learning theory.

S. Berezka (2021) focuses on the development of emotional intelligence among future special education professionals, advocating for the inclusion of emotional self-regulation modules and empathic communication training in professional curricula. Meanwhile, N. Kalaytan et al. (2020) explore the structural organization of PEI in students of humanities and technical fields, emphasizing discipline-specific tendencies in emotional expression, cognitive empathy, and social perspective-taking.

Situational learning, as shown by O. Romanovskyi et al. (2024), emerges as an effective strategy for PEI formation. Through the use of emotionally charged educational simulations and problem-based learning scenarios, students are placed in conditions that require them to analyze emotional dynamics, manage personal reactions, and interact

constructively with others. The authors demonstrate how such immersive approaches activate emotional-cognitive schemas and stimulate emotional learning.

4. Positive Psycho-Emotional Intelligence and the Educational Environment

A particularly innovative dimension is introduced in the studies of S. Tolochko & V. Vasiuk (2024a, 2024b, 2024c), who propose the concept of **positive psycho-emotional intelligence** – a framework that emphasizes the proactive development of emotional optimism, emotional creativity, and value-based emotional engagement. Their model integrates the cultivation of emotional literacy with the broader goals of multicultural education and personality development.

This approach includes such components as:

- Development of emotional resilience through narrative practices and life-design techniques.
- Enhancement of interpersonal sensitivity via cooperative learning, feedback rituals, and peer tutoring.
- Formation of value-based emotional identity, which allows students to perceive emotions as meaningful experiences integrated with ethical and cultural contexts.

Their work demonstrates that PEI should not merely be treated as an individual ability but as a pedagogical phenomenon embedded in institutional culture and academic discourse.

5. Research Outcomes and Scientific Justification

Based on the conducted analysis and synthesis of sources, the following key scientific outcomes can be identified:

- PEI is a multidimensional construct that must be addressed at all levels of the educational process – from curriculum design to instructional practice, from assessment systems to campus climate.
- Students with higher levels of PEI show enhanced cognitive-emotional integration, which supports their learning motivation, collaborative potential, and psychological well-being (N. Tkachenko, 2024).

– PEI is highly sensitive to pedagogical influence, particularly under the conditions of emotionally meaningful tasks, dialogue-based learning, and reflexive thinking (M. Avgustyuk, 2022; G. Murowska et al., 2025).

– There exists a pressing need for a unified methodological framework for PEI diagnostics and training in higher education, especially one that considers intercultural, gender, and discipline-specific aspects.

– The development of PEI contributes to the formation of an emotionally intelligent educational community, fostering sustainable student development and enriching the institutional mission of modern universities.

6. Practical Implementation and Future Directions

The practical implications of this study suggest that psycho-emotional intelligence should be systematically integrated into educational policies and instructional strategies.

This includes:

– Teacher training programs that equip educators with emotional intelligence tools and competencies.

– Curricular modules focused on emotional literacy, psychological self-care, and empathy training.

– Educational technologies (e.g., AI-based emotion tracking tools, gamified emotion regulation apps) to personalize emotional development and provide feedback loops.

– Collaborative learning formats such as project-based learning and peer mentoring that support emotional and social skill-building.

The modern educational environment must become a space for not only intellectual but also emotional cultivation, preparing students to navigate the challenges of an increasingly complex, emotionally demanding, and multicultural world.

Conclusions and further prospects in this area. The conducted theoretical and analytical research affirms that psycho-emotional intelligence (PEI) is not only a desirable personal trait but a strategically significant component of modern education, with profound

implications for students' cognitive development, psychological well-being, and professional readiness. The contemporary educational environment—characterized by digital transformation, increased emotional stress, and growing complexity of social interactions—demands that higher education institutions shift from purely knowledge-centric models to more holistic, emotionally intelligent learning ecosystems.

The key conclusions of the study can be summarized as follows:

PEI is a multidimensional construct, comprising emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, and social skills, all of which are vital for student success in the 21st century.

The development of PEI requires intentional pedagogical conditions, including emotionally supportive learning environments, reflective teaching practices, situational and experiential learning, and value-oriented education.

Positive psycho-emotional intelligence, as a newly proposed conceptual lens, provides an advanced framework for fostering emotional optimism, intercultural empathy, and personal integrity within student populations.

PEI development has a significant impact on various dimensions of students' functioning—academic engagement, stress resilience, communication skills, and future employability—making it a powerful tool for promoting sustainable human capital.

There is a critical gap in unified diagnostic tools and educational strategies, which hinders the systematic integration of PEI training in university curricula and teacher preparation programs.

The reviewed scientific literature and empirical data confirm that PEI can and should be cultivated through pedagogically sound, evidence-based, and context-sensitive interventions within formal and non-formal education settings.

Building on the identified conclusions, several promising directions for future research and practical innovation emerge. Development of a unified model of PEI formation tailored to the needs of different academic disciplines (humanities, STEM, education, etc.), with a focus on developmental and cultural sensitivity. Design of adaptive digital platforms

and AI-assisted tools for the personalized development and real-time monitoring of emotional intelligence in educational settings.

Ultimately, the systematic cultivation of psycho-emotional intelligence among students is not only a pedagogical imperative but a societal necessity, ensuring the emergence of emotionally resilient, socially responsible, and ethically grounded future professionals. As educational environments continue to evolve, PEI will remain a cornerstone of adaptive, human-centered, and future-oriented pedagogy.

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